

**RE.
CAP**

Reinforcing CAP

PROJECT ACRONYM: RECAP

PROJECT NUMBER: 693171

PROJECT FULL TITLE: Personalised public services in support of the implementation of the CAP

WORK PACKAGE NUMBER & NAME:

WP.5 Dissemination & Exploitation

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The project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Programme under Grant Agreement No. 693171.

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1. PROJECT VISUAL IDENTITY AND SLOGAN

logo

"The RECAP logo is inspired by the natural environment and agriculture. The leaf is multiplied, representing land fertility, agricultural investment and enhancing the environment. Agricultural land is gradually being formed. Every leaf represents the concept of multiple information that is combined, intersected and diffused to all interested parties as a single integrated whole. This logic includes also the concept of the cross-compliance mechanism. The circle formed in the end is the position stigma, the focus, the target. The hues signify all stages of production (from young seedlings to ready for harvest). Choosing cool colors for the logo give a sense of professionalism. The green color is very close to earth; it represents a new beginning and growth, but also expresses its renewal and abundance. The blue is extensively used to represent responsibility and darker shades of blue are used in the project acronym, in order to attest credibility".

Certain elements such as the distinctive logo, the brand motto - slogan, and the specific chromatic choices, form the RECAP visual identity. These elements create a memorable image, as well as a clear message in order to ensure that the target groups easily recall the project and its orientation. All partners are expected to apply the logo in the dissemination activities and respective publications to facilitate recognition of RECAP and thus increase its impact. The logo chosen is clear, captures the attention of the target groups and communicates the main concepts of RECAP.

In particular, all dissemination material of RECAP will demonstrate the RECAP logo, the EU emblem, and a clear statement that the project has received funding from the Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme.

The EU emblem accompanied by the text below will be added as follows:

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 693171.

In order to communicate a coherent message towards the target groups, RECAP is linked with a catchy slogan as a mean to draw attention. The majority of the RECAP partners agreed that this slogan will be the: ***"Reinforcing CAP"***.

various banners

Various online and offline project banners were created in order to enhance the graphical identity of the project and facilitate the communication of the main ideas of the project. The banners were developed based on their power to generate awareness, raise curiousness and motivate to participate in the project activities. It is envisioned to use these banners on the project's website, newsletters, leaflets, social media accounts, etc.

deliverables' template

For the needs of the preparation of the project's deliverables, a deliverable template has been produced in an MS Word format using a certain style. The purpose of such a template is to have a consistent and recognisable layout for the project's deliverables.

The deliverable template has a cover page that displays the project's logo in a prominent position, its Acronym, Number, Full Title, as well as the work Package Number and Deliverable Number and Name. At the bottom of the page there is a clear statement that the project has received funding from the EU along with the emblem of the EU as required in the Article 29.4 of the Grant Agreement.

The second page of the template includes a table with the document's information (Grant Agreement Number, Acronym, Project Full Title, Start Date, Duration, Project URL, Deliverable Number & Name, Work Package Number & Name, Date of Delivery, Nature, Dissemination Level, Lead Beneficiary, Responsible Author and Contributions from) and a table with the document's history. Moreover, it contains a disclaimer that excludes the responsibility of the European Commission for any use that may be made of the information contained in any deliverable as required by Grant Agreement Article 29.5. In the same page a copyright message is displayed in order to protect the originality of any produced content within the RECAP project.

The third page of the template is reserved for the tables of contents and figures. The first three pages of the template remain static, do not change and contain only the information mentioned above. The header of the template for the rest of the pages contains the project logo, the EU emblem and the Deliverable and Work Package Number and Name, whereas the footer includes the numbering of the document pages.

REoCAP Reinforcing CAP

WP number Title
D number Title

Table of Contents

- 1. TEXT4
- 2. TEXT5
- 2.1 Text5
 - 2.1.1 Text5
 - 2.1.1.1 Text5
 - 2.1.2 Text5
 - 2.1.2.1 Text5

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REoCAP Reinforcing CAP

WP number Title
D number Title

1. TEXT

Text

1.1 Text

1.1.1 Text

1.1.1.1 Text

1.1.1.1.1 Text

1.1.2 Text

1.1.2.1 Text

1.1.2.1.1 Text

TABLE TITLE

Text	Text	Text	Text
Text			
Text			
Text			

SOURCE text

Page 4/6

presentations template

The RECAP presentations are part of the different dissemination tools designed to support the RECAP dissemination efforts. The presentation template will be used in the project meetings and all events and meetings where RECAP results and activities are presented and it was designed following the graphic identity orientation to facilitate the recognition of the project.

2. PRESS RELEASE

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Personalised public services
in support of the implementation of the CAP

Press Release

● ● ●

For further information on the project please contact the RECAP team at
info@recap-h2020.eu

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3. PROJECT WEBSITE

“WELCOME” page

https://www.recap-h2020.eu

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HOME ABOUT PILOTS THE PLATFORM RESOURCES NEWS & EVENTS CONTACT

NEWS & EVENTS

February 8, 2017

EMPLOYMENT, SOCIAL AFFAIRS & INCLUSION

Published by [Ioanna Antonopoulou](#) Categories

Blueprint for sectoral cooperation on skills: Space (Geo Information)

A new framework for strategic cooperation to address short and medium-term skills needs in a given economic sector.

0 Read more

February 7, 2017

ENVIRONMENT

Published by [Ioanna Antonopoulou](#) Categories

Environmental Implementation Review: New way to help Member States apply EU rules benefits citizens, administrations and economy

https://www.recap-h2020.eu

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HOME ABOUT PILOTS THE PLATFORM RESOURCES NEWS & EVENTS CONTACT

Copernicus programmes in agriculture, was decided on Monday 23rd January at International Green Week in Berlin.

0 Read more

HORIZON 2020

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QUICK FINDER

- ABOUT PROJECT
- PILOTS
- THE PLATFORM
- RELATED PROJECTS
- NEWS & EVENTS
- CONTACT

ReCAP on Social Media

f t in

yt y+ u

Contact Us: info@recap-h2020.eu

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Worx

“ABOUT” section

https://www.recap-h2020.eu/about/project-summary/

REoCAP Reinforcing CAP

HOME ABOUT PILOTS THE PLATFORM RESOURCES NEWS & EVENTS CONTACT

▶ ABOUT PROJECT ◀

Background

The EU policy tool for integrating environmental requirements into the **Common Agricultural Policy** is the **Cross Compliance Scheme**. EU farmers shall respect cross-compliance rules, legislative standards and obligations, in order to receive payments, but more importantly cross-compliance enhances awareness among them and helps European farming to be more compatible with the expectations of society. Farmers' non-compliance with standards may lead to reduction or, even, cancellation of their agricultural support and rural development payments.

The overall objective is to develop and pilot test a platform for the delivery of public services that will enable the improved implementation of the CAP, targeting public Paying Agencies, agricultural consultants and farmers. The platform will collect information:

- from open satellite data,
- through farmers' mobile devices,
- from commercial channels of satellite data providers.

https://www.recap-h2020.eu/about/work-packages/

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HOME ABOUT PILOTS THE PLATFORM RESOURCES NEWS & EVENTS CONTACT

▶ WORK PACKAGES ◀

- + WP1 - Project Management
- + WP2 - Users' needs analysis & co-production of services
- + WP3 - Service integration and customization
- + WP4 - Deployment and operation

“PILOTS” section

“THE PLATFORM” section

“RESOURCES” section

“NEWS & EVENTS” section

The screenshot shows a web browser displaying the RECAP website. The URL in the address bar is <https://www.recap-h2020.eu/events/>. The page features a navigation menu with links for HOME, ABOUT, PILOTS, THE PLATFORM, RESOURCES, NEWS & EVENTS, and CONTACT. The main content area is titled "EVENTS" and contains a list of events:

- + Project Kick-off Meeting
- 2nd Project Meeting
- 2nd Project Meeting - Heraklion, Greece, 3-4 November 2016

The footer includes the HORIZON 2020 logo, a funding acknowledgment: "This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Programme under Grant Agreement No. 693171", a QUICK FINDER menu with links to ABOUT PROJECT, PILOTS, and THE PLATFORM, and social media icons for Facebook, Twitter, and LinkedIn.

“CONTACT” section

The screenshot shows a web browser window displaying the contact page of the RECAP website. The browser's address bar shows the URL <https://www.recap-h2020.eu/contact/>. The website header includes the RECAP logo and a navigation menu with links for HOME, ABOUT, PILOTS, THE PLATFORM, RESOURCES, NEWS & EVENTS, and CONTACT. The main content area is titled "CONTACT" and is divided into two sections: "Contact Details" and "Newsletter Form".

Contact Details:
Email: info@recap-h2020.eu

Newsletter Form:
SIGN UP to receive the RECAP Newsletter, with all the latest news on the Project.

The contact form includes the following fields:

- Your name
- Your e-mail
- Subject
- Message

The newsletter form includes the following field:

- Your e-mail address

A "Submit" button is located below the newsletter form field.

4. SOCIAL MEDIA

facebook page

twitter account

linkedin group

yammer group

slideshare account

youtube Channel

5. BANNER ROLL UP

7. FACTSHEET

PERSONALISED PUBLIC SERVICES IN SUPPORT OF THE IMPLEMENTATION OF THE CAP

REoCAP
Reinforcing CAP

REoCAP
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RECAP is an innovation project that aims at developing improved remote monitoring of CAP obligations and at supplementing in-field inspections by Payment Agencies.

www.recap-h2020.eu

GOALS

- Develop and pilot test a platform for the delivery of public services.
- Enable an improved implementation of the CAP.
- Improve remote monitoring of CAP obligations.
- Supplement the in-field inspections by the Payment Agencies.
- Make cross-compliance more efficient.
- Offer farmers the ability to comply with regulations.
- Enable agricultural consultants to develop their own services.
- Reduce the administrative burdens.

KEY ISSUES

The integration of environmental concerns into the CAP results many burdens both for the public authorities (high administrative costs due to the need of in-field visits) and the farmers (difficulties in familiarising and dealing with the applicable regulations).
The RECAP project enables a better implementation of the CAP and increases the transparency of compliance monitoring procedures related to the CAP.

TECHNICAL APPROACH

RECAP will be a cloud-based Software as a Service (SaaS) platform which will collect information from open satellite data and commercial channels of satellite data providers. It will extract useful features from earth observation, correlate them with user-generated and geo-information data and model this information for enabling the identification of potential breaches of compliance.

PERSONALISED PUBLIC SERVICES IN SUPPORT OF THE IMPLEMENTATION OF THE CAP

EXPECTED ACHIEVEMENTS

RECAP will offer farmers a tool supporting them to comply with regulations and enable agricultural consultants to develop their own services within the platform using tools and communication with the database under an open approach. Paying agencies will benefit through less administrative work providing at the same time enhanced transparency in the CAP monitoring procedure.

IMPACT

Stimulate the creation, delivery and use of new services on a variety of devices, utilising new web technologies coupled with open public data.

- Provide more personalised public services that better suit the users' needs.
- Reduce the administrative burden of citizens and businesses.
- Increase transparency of and trust in public administrations.

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8. BROCHURE

RECAP Reinforcing CAP

PERSONALISED PUBLIC SERVICES IN SUPPORT OF THE IMPLEMENTATION OF THE CAP

#RECAP H2020 Project

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www.recap-h2020.eu

THE IDEA BEHIND RECAP

The need for a sustainable future, has led progressively to the integration of environmental concerns into the Common Agricultural Policy (CAP). Since 2003, EU farmers receiving direct payments are subject to the 'Cross-Compliance' scheme, a set of compulsory legislative standards and obligations. These CAP rules are legislative standards and obligations in the field of the environment and a non-compliance may lead to reduction or even cancellation of payments. However, pursuing the integration of environmental concerns into the CAP and making it more compatible with the expectations of society, results many burdens both for the public authorities and the farmers. On the one hand, the public administrative costs are high due to the need of in-field visits and on the other hand, farmers face difficulties in familiarising and dealing with the applicable regulations. As a broad range of technological advances benefit agriculture, remote sensing and ICT, offer the possibility to reduce the dependence on labour and time-intensive work. The idea behind RECAP is to combine remote sensing technology within a modern ICT platform and get a service tool for all stakeholders involved in the cross-compliance scheme (farmers, agricultural consultants, paying agencies). The project started in May 2016 and is supported by Horizon 2020 programme 'ICT-enabled open government'.

PROJECT'S AIMS

The RECAP project, aims to develop an improved monitoring of the CAP obligations and make cross-compliance more efficient. RECAP aspires to offer farmers the ability to comply with regulations, enable agricultural consultants to develop their own services within the platform and reduce the administrative burdens for the Paying Agencies. Overall RECAP's vision is to:

- Help Paying Agencies to carry out checks for cross-compliance more efficiently, accurately & faster, and therefore reduce the administrative burden.
- Increase transparency by assisting farmers to better understand how to ensure compliance.
- Allow agricultural consultants to create new added value services.
- Facilitate synergies with other initiatives, ensuring the efficient communication and understanding of the RECAP project.
- Encourage involvement of stakeholders and the wide public, safeguarding the transferability of results.

RECAP H2020 Project

ACTIVITIES

Public administrations responsible for the implementation of the Common Agricultural Policy (CAP) need to monitor farmers' compliance to standards. Monitoring is performed by in-field visits and through remote sensing. RECAP proposes a methodology for improving the efficiency and transparency of the compliance monitoring procedure through a cloud-based Software as a Service (SaaS) platform which will make use of large volumes of publicly available data provided by satellite remote sensing, and user-generated data provided by farmers through mobile devices (geo-referenced and time-stamped photos). The RECAP platform will extract useful features from Earth observation open data, correlate them with user-generated and geo-information data available to public organisations, and model this information for enabling the identification of potential breaches of compliance by public authorities and inspectors. RECAP will offer farmers a tool supporting them to comply with regulations imposed by the CAP, providing personalised information for simplifying the interpretation of complex regulations, and early alerts on potential breaches. RECAP will allow agricultural consultants and developers to create add-ons to the main application that extend its functionality and exploit the data collected through an Application Programming Interface (API), and a Software Development Kit (SDK). Consultants will be able to access data available in the platform, subject to security and privacy policies, and to develop their own services within the platform using design tools, libraries, and communication with the database under an open approach. The RECAP services will be tested and validated in an operational environment in 5 countries with the participation of public authorities, farmers, and agricultural consultants.

EXPECTED RESULTS

- Stimulate the creation, delivery and use of new services on a variety of devices, utilising new web technologies coupled with open public data.
- Provide more personalised public services that better suit the needs of users.
- Reduce the administrative burden of citizens and businesses.
- Increase transparency of and trust in public administrations.

RECAP will manage to harness the benefits of remote sensing data which, combined with user-generated data, will enable the improved implementation of the CAP. To this end Control and Payment Agencies will manage more efficient checks for cross compliance by modernising the monitoring procedure and at same time reducing administrative burden in processing data for inspections. Agricultural consultants and farmers associations will receive personalised support on how farmers could increase the productivity of their holdings, and on how they can comply with the Cross Compliance Scheme. Finally farmers' administrative burden in dealing with procedures for payments will be reduced, while they will be better prepared for inspections given that general guidance on how to ensure compliance and access to up-to-date information on regulations will be available through the RECAP application.

Overall CAP monitoring procedures will increase in transparency and accountability.

9. POSTER

PERSONALISED PUBLIC SERVICES IN SUPPORT OF THE IMPLEMENTATION OF THE CAP

RECAP

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